

ANTIFUNGAL EFFECT OF CHITOSAN DERIVATIVES SOLUTIONS AGAINST STRAIN OF *FUSARIUM OXYSPORUM****Asrakulova D.I., Rasnidova S.Sh., Vokhidova N.R., Pirniyazov K.K.*****Institute of Polymer Chemistry and Physics Academy of the Science of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, Uzbekistan**

The battle against pathogens, particularly illnesses, is crucial to achieving high-quality and high yields from agricultural products. Root rot disease is caused by a *Fusarium oxysporum* infection. The illness affects plant sprouts, and a new, unique type of fungus was discovered in Spain in 2014 year. Plant germination occurs when the disease causes the most damage to plants.

Fusarium oxysporum wilt damages these crops during every stage of their growth and development. Plants are infected by the fungus, which grows inside their xylem tubes. During the day, infected plants seem pale and eventually completely wither. The plant withers because the toxins secreted by the disease poison it, and the conducting tubes are clogged with fungal mycelia, preventing water from passing through them. Yellow, brown, and brown patches are observed when the roots and stems of wilted plants are cut; however, these spots are not always visible [1]. Plants that are infected but not wilted exhibit weak and stunted growth, with few and subpar fruits. A lack of moisture causes fusarium wilt, which has a serious negative impact on crops. During the growing season, *Fusarium oxysporum* does not develop mycelia, chlamydospores, or conidia on infected living plants; however, it does create large quantities on dead plants.

A poisonous material with the capacity to eradicate the pathogen that causes sickness is the basis of a chemical approach. Importantly, the majority of chemical fungicides utilized pose less of a risk to both people and animals. However, they enter the body through the stomach, intestines, and respiratory system and accumulate in the liver, kidneys, lungs, and heart. They may poison you both acutely and over time. The acute toxicity of fungicides to warm-blooded animals serves as a proxy for their risk to human health.

Biologically active polymers based on chitosan (CS) have been found to be extremely effective against a variety of hazardous infections while remaining safe for both humans and the environment, according to an analysis of foreign scientific literature. The use of chitosan nanoparticles (CSNPs) has proven to be one of the most promising and eco-friendly preparations in various disciplines in recent decades [2, 4].

Fusarium oxysporum cultures of microscopic fungi belonging to the genus were placed in a thermostat at a temperature of 25–30 °C for 3 cycles. The effective zones of the drugs were determined within 48–72 hours. To measure the fungal zone scale accurately, the PW297-200 ×95 mm compact (package size) antibiotic zone reading scale kit developed by Hi Media was used [3, 5, 6] (Fig.1.).

1- UZKHITAN 2%, 2- Initial CS 0.5%, 3- AOCS 4:1 0.5%, 4- Ascorbic acid 0.5%, 5- NACS 4:1 0.5%, 6- $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ 7- NACS: $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ 0.5%, 8- Cu_2O/CuO 0.1%, 9- Copper oxide 0.5%, 10- Nanocitrate CS 3:1:0.5, 11- Nanocitrate CS 4:1:0.5%.

Fig. 1. Antifungal properties of chitosan derivative solutions against a strain of *Fusarium oxysporum*

Preparations based on chitosan interact with the surface of the pathogen, alter the permeability of the cell membrane, or obstruct the flow of chemicals that are needed. Products derived from chitosan interact with cytoplasmic elements such as nutrients, metal ions, and minerals to inhibit the growth of infections.

The fungicidal effects of chitosan-based medications against *F. oxysporum* were investigated in pure fungal cultures. After adding 4×10^5 or 800,000 pieces of fungus (cell) solutions to a Petri dish, the growth of the fungus mycelia around the sections was monitored for 48–72 hours. The high fungicidal capabilities of nanocitrate Chs in the 4:1 40–41.5 mm zone and NACS: $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ are beneficial for the development of fungal mycelia.

References

1. Turdieva D.T., Dehkonova M.P. “Cucumber fusariosis and its methods treatments” International scientific-practical conference actual issues of agricultural development: problems and solutions, June 6-7, Tashkent, 2023.
2. Sahab F., Waly A.I., Sabbour M.M., Nawar L.S. “Synthesis, antifungal and insecticidal potential of chitosan (CS)-g-poly (acrylic acid) (PAA) nanoparticles against some seed borne fungi and insects of soybean”. *Int. J. ChemTech Res.*, 8 (2015), pp. 589-598.
3. Hasheminejad N., Khodaiyan F., Safari M. “Improving the antifungal activity of clove essential oil encapsulated by chitosan nanoparticles”. *Food Chem.*, 275 (2019), pp. 113-122, 10.1016/j.foodchem.2018.09.085.
4. Kalagatur N.K., Nirmal Ghosh O.S., Sundararaj N., Mudili V. “Antifungal activity of chitosan nanoparticles encapsulated with *Cymbopogon martinii* essential oil on plant pathogenic fungi *Fusarium graminearum*”. *Front. Pharmacol.*, 9 (2018), pp. 1-13, 10.3389/fphar.2018.00610.
5. Egorov N.S. A guide to practical classes in microbiology. Moscow State University, Moscow, 1995, 205 p.
6. Egorov N.S. Fundamentals of teaching of antibiotics. Moscow State University, Moscow, 2003, 104 p.